

EXPLORING THE NATIONAL LEARNING CAMP ON STUDENTS' MATHEMATICS PERFORMANCE: A CONVERGENT PARALLEL ANALYSIS

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ABSTRACT

This study explored the *perceived effectiveness* of the *National Learning Camp (NLC)* on students' *mathematics achievement* using a *mixed-methods approach*. Quantitative data revealed that students generally perceived the NLC as very effective across several areas, including *engagement and participation*, *student satisfaction*, *resource utilization*, continuity, and sustainability, with a grand mean of 6.09. Notably, *teacher support* was extremely effective, indicating that students highly valued the support they received from their teachers during the NLC. The average *academic achievement* in mathematics across the schools was satisfactory. Qualitative findings highlighted that student experienced increased *enjoyment and engagement*, and improved understanding of math concepts through the NLC's activities and *teacher support*. However, they also faced physical and financial barriers such as transportation issues, *lack of resources*, *household responsibilities*, and *low motivation*, which affected their learning. A *weak positive correlation* was found between the *perceived effectiveness* of the NLC and students' *academic achievement* in mathematics, suggesting that while perception plays a role, other factors also influence student outcomes. The NLC was generally perceived positively by students and contributed to improved skills and confidence. However, addressing *logistical challenges*, incorporating *varied teaching strategies*, and providing differentiated instruction are important for enhancing its impact on *mathematics achievement* and ensuring more *equitable access to learning*.

Keywords: *National Learning Camp (NLC), Mathematics achievement, Mixed-methods approach, Perceived effectiveness, Engagement and participation, Student satisfaction, Resource utilization, Continuity and sustainability, Teacher support, academic achievement, Enjoyment and engagement, Lack of resources, Household responsibilities, Low motivation, Logistical challenges, Differentiated instruction, Equitable access to learning, student engagement, academic performance*

INTRODUCTION

Background of the Study

The COVID-19 pandemic has led to one of education's most significant global disruptions, affecting more than 1.6 billion students across 190 countries (UNESCO, 2022). Prolonged school closures and the sudden shift to remote learning have created severe learning deficits, particularly in foundational subjects such as mathematics and reading (World Bank, 2022). According to the World Bank (2022), learning poverty, defined as the percentage of children unable to read and understand a simple text by age 10, has risen to an alarming 70% in low- and middle-income countries due to the pandemic. Mathematics, a critical foundation for science, technology, engineering, and mathematics (STEM) education, has also been significantly impacted, with learning losses ranging from 0.3 to 1.1 years of schooling across different regions (Azevedo et al., 2021).

The global learning crisis in mathematics is not new but has been exacerbated by the pandemic. Before COVID-19, numerous countries faced challenges in achieving quality mathematics education due to inadequate teacher training, insufficient resources, and inequitable access to learning materials (Mullis et al., 2016). The pandemic has compounded these pre-existing issues, leading to further declines in students' mathematical competencies, especially in underserved and marginalized communities (UNICEF, 2022). As a result, countries worldwide have been compelled to implement innovative learning recovery strategies to address these growing educational gaps. For instance, high-dosage tutoring, summer learning programs, extended school days, and blended learning models have been introduced in various contexts to help students catch up on lost learning (Kuhfeld et al., 2020; Nickow, Oreopoulos, & Quan, 2020).

In the Philippine context, the impact of the pandemic on education has been profound. The Philippines has one of the longest school closures globally, with schools remaining closed for in-person classes for over two academic years (UNICEF Philippines, 2022). It has resulted in significant learning losses, particularly in mathematics, where Filipino students struggled before the pandemic. The 2018 Programme for International Student Assessment (PISA) ranked the Philippines last in mathematics among 79 participating countries, highlighting systemic issues in the quality of math education (OECD, 2019). These issues include inadequate teacher training, *lack of resources*, and a curriculum that does not fully engage students in critical thinking and problem-solving (Santos & Reyes, 2023).

In response to these challenges, the Department of Education (DepEd) in the Philippines has launched the *National Learning Camp (NLC)* as part of its Learning Recovery Plan to mitigate learning losses and improve *academic performance*, particularly in mathematics (DepEd, 2023). The NLC aims to provide focused, supplementary learning support through various interactive, student-centered activities designed to help students recover from learning gaps caused by the pandemic. The camp is typically conducted during school breaks. It employs innovative teaching strategies, such as collaborative learning, *differentiated instruction*, and educational technology, to enhance students' engagement and understanding of mathematical concepts (Reyes & Bautista, 2024).

The NLC program is designed to address immediate learning gaps and build foundational mathematics skills crucial for students' long-term academic success. According to DepEd (2023), the program targets students who have fallen behind in their grade-level competencies, providing them with a structured environment to catch up on essential mathematical skills. Initial reports from pilot implementations of the NLC indicate positive outcomes, such as improved *student engagement*, a better grasp of mathematical concepts, and higher confidence levels in mathematics (DepEd, 2023). However, despite these promising early results, there is a lack of comprehensive empirical research evaluating the overall effectiveness of the NLC program in improving students' *academic performance* in mathematics.

Hence, rigorous research is needed to evaluate its effectiveness and provide actionable insights for future program enhancements. This study aims to fill this gap by providing empirical evidence on the impact of the NLC on students' *academic performance* in mathematics, thereby contributing to the ongoing efforts to rebuild and strengthen educational systems in the Philippines and beyond.

Theoretical Framework

The present study is related to three theories: constructivist Learning Theory, *Differentiated Instruction* Theory, and Bloom's Mastery Learning Theory.

The Constructivist Learning Theory (Piaget, 1954; Vygotsky, 1978) emphasizes that learning is an active, constructive process in which students build knowledge through experiences. The NLC's student-centered and interactive learning activities resonate with this theory, as they promote hands-on experiences, collaboration, and the development of critical thinking skills, which are essential for a deep understanding of mathematics (Piaget, 1954; Vygotsky, 1978).

The Differentiated Instruction Theory (Tomlinson, 2001) aligns with the NLC's approach of tailoring educational interventions to meet learners' varied needs. This theory advocates customizing instruction based on students' abilities and learning styles. It needs to optimize academic success, a key strategy employed in the NLC to address learning gaps in mathematics (Tomlinson, 2001).

Bloom's Mastery Learning Theory (Bloom, 1968) supports the idea that students can achieve mastery with the necessary time, feedback, and instructional conditions. The NLC's focus on providing targeted interventions and ensuring students master essential mathematical concepts reflects the principles of mastery learning, suggesting that, given adequate support, all students can achieve high levels of performance (Bloom, 1968).

This study is also related to the efficacy of the *National Learning Camp (NLC)*. It explored its impact on literacy and numeracy skills, revealing positive early outcomes. Students who participated in the program demonstrated improved engagement and understanding of mathematical and literacy concepts. The program employed interactive, student-centered methods, such as collaborative learning and differentiated instruction, to address learning gaps. However, the study also highlighted the need for more rigorous research to assess the long-term effectiveness of the NLC on *academic performance*.

Conceptual Framework

This study is anchored on three key theories: Constructivist Learning Theory (Piaget, 1954; Vygotsky, 1978), which emphasizes active learning and knowledge construction through hands-on experiences and collaboration, aligning with the NLC's interactive approach; Differentiated Instruction Theory (Tomlinson, 2001), advocating for customized instruction based on individual needs, as practiced in the NLC; and Bloom's Mastery Learning Theory (Bloom, 1968), which supports the idea that all students can achieve mastery with appropriate time, feedback, and targeted interventions.

In this study, the dependent variable is students' *academic achievement* in mathematics, which reflects how well students perform in math as influenced by various factors.

While the independent variables are the different aspects of the NLC that are believed to impact this achievement. These includes: *Perceived effectiveness* of the NLC – how students rate the overall success of the program; *Student engagement and participation* – the level of involvement and interest students show during the camp; *Student satisfaction* – how content students are with the learning experience; *Resource utilization* – how effectively learning materials and tools are used; *Continuity and sustainability* – the consistency and long-term viability of the program; *Teacher support* – the guidance and assistance provided by educators; *Enjoyment and motivation* – emotional and psychological factors that influence learning; *Barriers to learning* – challenges such as transportation, financial constraints, and *household responsibilities*.

These independent variables are examined to understand their influence on the dependent variable—*mathematics achievement*. The study found a *weak positive correlation*, suggesting that while students' perceptions of the NLC contribute to their performance, other external factors also play a significant role.

Research Questions

The study evaluated the *perceived effectiveness* of the *National Learning Camp (NLC)* implemented by the DepEd on students' academic performance in mathematics. It answered the following questions:

1. What is the level of effectiveness as perceived by the students on the National Learning Camp in terms of:
 - 1.1 *engagement and participation*;
 - 1.2 *teacher support*;
 - 1.3 students' satisfaction;
 - 1.4 *resource utilization*; and
 - 1.5 *continuity and sustainability*?
2. What is the *academic performance* of the students in Mathematics?
3. Is there a significant relationship between the *perceived effectiveness* of the NLC and students' *academic performance* in Mathematics?
4. How do students perceive the influence of the NLC on their performance in Mathematics?
5. What challenges do students experience in NLC and how do these challenges affect students' learning outcomes in Mathematics?
6. How is the perceived level of effectiveness of the NLC and *academic performance* associated with students' experiences and challenges in learning Mathematics?

METHODOLOGY

Research Design

This study used a convergent parallel mixed-method design to examine the relationships between participation in the *National Learning Camp (NLC)* and students' *academic performance* in Mathematics. According to Creswell and Plano Clark (2011), mixed methods convergent parallel design involves collecting quantitative and qualitative data simultaneously to validate or corroborate findings from each data type. This approach enables a comprehensive understanding of the research phenomenon by integrating the strengths of both quantitative and qualitative methods (Creswell, 2015).

In the context of this study, the mixed methods convergent parallel design is well-suited for examining how various aspects of the NLC experience, such as *engagement and participation*, teacher approach, students' satisfaction, *resource utilization*, and *continuity and sustainability*, correlate with students' mathematical achievement. Quantitative data were collected through surveys and assessments to measure *academic performance* in mathematics and the *perceived effectiveness* of the NLC. Correlation analysis determined the strength and direction of the relationships between these variables. Simultaneously, qualitative data were gathered through student interviews, providing in-depth insights into their experiences and perceptions of the NLC. This qualitative component helped contextualize the quantitative findings, offering a richer

understanding of how the NLC influences students' mathematical learning. By combining both data types, the study can present a more comprehensive picture of the NLC's effectiveness and identify areas for improvement.

Locale of the Study

The study was conducted in chosen secondary schools in Bagumbayan, Sultan Kudarat, where the NLC program was implemented, and the researcher was actively involved. This location was chosen because it represents secondary schools participating in the Department of Education (DepEd) activities and is easily accessible for data gathering. Bagumbayan has seven secondary schools, including Busok National High School (NHS), Bai Saripinang NHS, Kapaya NHS, Bagumbayan NHS, Sumilil NHS, Masiag NHS, and Datu Matilondo Galmac NHS. All seven schools were included in the study because of their varied student population, prior educational program adoption, verified academic advances, and available baseline data.

Among the seven schools, Bagumbayan National High School ranks first, followed by Busok National High School, in terms of *academic achievement* in mathematics, as evidenced by the results of math Olympics, math camp contests, and Kidlat Talas contests sponsored by the local power provider, SUKELCO.

In terms of the number of participants who join the NLC program, Masiag National High School has the most number of participants (68 out of 387), which is 18% of their total population, followed by Sumilil National High School with 16% (28 out of 175), Kapaya NHS with 14% (54 out of 396), Bai Saripinang NHS with 13% (105 out of 803), Busok NHS with 12% (80 out of 685), Bagumbayan NHS with 9% (151 out of 1649), and finally the Datu Matilondo Galmac NHS with only 4% (66). This indicates that 9-18% of students were having difficulty learning due to these learning gaps.

Respondents of the Study

This study's respondents were randomly selected students who participated in the NLC program at the secondary school of Bagumbayan, Sultan Kudarat. The table below shows the sample size of the respondents in every school included in the study.

The sample determination formula / and Slovin's formula were used to calculate the sample size. Using this formula

$$n = \frac{N}{1 + N(e^2)}$$

where n = sample size, N = total population size, and e = margin of error (expressed as a decimal, e.g., 0.05 for 5%)

Table 1. Study Respondents

	School	Population	Proportion (%)	Sample Size
1	Busok NHS	80	14%	34
2	Bai Saripinang NHS	105	19%	44
3	Kapaya NHS	54	10%	23
4	Bagumbayan NHS	151	27%	63
5	Sumilil NHS	28	5%	12
6	Masiag NHS	68	12%	28
7	Datu Matilendo Galmac NHS	66	12%	28
	Total	552		232

Aside from the students, NLC teachers, coordinators, and administrators were included among the study's respondents because their insights were essential for interpreting how the camp influences students and the program. Teachers apply the NLC curriculum and engage directly with students, offering firsthand knowledge of its efficacy. Coordinators were essential to the camp's management and organization since they provided insight into its operational facets. Administrators, especially school leaders, can provide information about how the NLC is supported within the educational system and how it fits the school's overarching objectives.

Sampling Procedure

Creswell (2012) asserts that the best method for reducing bias is to combine stratified sampling with probability sampling. It was guaranteed that various demographic segments were represented by sampling inside each stratum. This sample method makes the analysis more accurate and representative.

To ensure representation across different grade levels and student characteristics, students who took part in the NLC were chosen for this study using a stratified random sample technique. A sample determination formula was used to calculate the sample size. The selection of NLC instructors, coordinators, and school administrators was based on their acquaintance with the *academic achievement* of the students and their involvement in the NLC program

Research Instrument

Data was collected through a questionnaire, academic records, and interviews. The survey assessed student demographic characteristics, educational profiles, and their perception of the influence of the NLC. *Academic performance* data, including grades, were obtained from school records to analyze changes in performance. Questionnaires were distributed to the respondents to gather needed quantitative information, and interviews were designed to gather qualitative information about NLC. The two instruments to collect data and information were researcher-made instruments patterned from the work of Creswell (2014). The instrument was subjected to validation to establish its reliability.

Reliability and validation were crucial in research to ensure the integrity and validity of data and conclusions. While reliability refers to the accuracy and consistency of the instrument's results, validation, on the other hand, verifies that a research instrument measures what it is supposed to measure. Despite these, research findings may be inaccurate and deceptive, and result in incorrect conclusions.

The 7-point Hedonic Scale was used to describe the students' perceptions of NLC's effectiveness. Below is the numerical rating used in the questionnaire, along with its corresponding interval values and descriptive interpretation.

Scale Point	Verbal Description	Score Interval	Effectiveness Level	Interpretation
7	Strongly Agree	6.15 – 7.00	Extremely Effective	Exceeded all expectations; very high impact and success.
6	Agree	5.30 - 6.14	Very Effective	Strong positive results; performed above expectations.
5	Somewhat Agree	4.44 - 5.29	Effective	Met expectations; achieved desired outcomes.
4	Neutral	3.58 - 4.43	Neutral	Neither effective nor ineffective; moderate or unclear results.
3	Somewhat Disagree	2.72 - 3.57	Ineffective	Marginally beneficial; failed to fully meet goals.
2	Disagree	1.87 - 2.71	Very Ineffective	Minimal benefit; largely failed to deliver expected outcomes.

1	Strongly Disagree	1.00 - 1.86	Extremely Ineffective	No benefit; negative or counterproductive effect.
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The hedonic scale was originally developed for sensory evaluation (Peryam & Pilgrim, 1957) and is widely used in consumer research. When adapted to effectiveness assessment, it functions as an attitude.

The grading scale below indicates the degree of students' accomplishments in Mathematics. Under the K to 12 Basic Education Program, the Department of Education (DepEd) Philippines employs a competency-based grading system. Here is a simplified summary of the DepEd Grading Scale as of 2024 (DepEd Order No. 8, s. 2015).

Description	Grading Scale	Remarks
Outstanding	90 – 100	Passed
Very Satisfactory	85 – 89	Passed
Satisfactory	80 – 84	Passed
Fairly Satisfactory	75 – 79	Passed
Did Not Meet Expectations	Below 75	Failed

The following was used to determine the significant correlation between *perceived effectiveness* and achievement (Lei et al,2018).

Pearson r Correlation Coefficient	Interpretation
0.00 – 0.10	Negligible Correlation
0.11 – 0.39	Weak Correlation
0.40 – 0.69	Moderate Correlation
0.70 – 0.89	Strong Correlation
0.90 – 1.00	Very Strong Correlation

Data Gathering Procedure

Creswell and Guetterman (2019) highlight the significance of qualitative data-gathering methods in understanding complex phenomena, capturing detailed descriptions of participants' experiences, and exploring new areas. They emphasize the flexibility of qualitative research, which involves interviews, observations, and document analysis to identify patterns and themes. Validity and reliability were ensured through triangulation and member checking, while ethical considerations included obtaining informed consent, confidentiality, and sensitivity to power dynamics between researchers and participants.

School administrators and the DepEd sought initial permission and coordination to access student academic records and distribute surveys in the data-gathering procedure. The permission was granted. Surveys were distributed to students, teachers, and administrators, with responses collected in person. *Academic performance* data, including mathematics grades, were collected from school records of NLC participants.

Additionally, supplemental qualitative data were gathered through interviews to gain deeper insights into instructional strategies and school support mechanisms related to the NLC program.

Statistical Treatment

Data was processed and analyzed using the free and open-source statistical analysis software designed to be user-friendly and accessible, especially for students, educators, and researchers, Jeffreys's Amazing Statistics Program (JASP) software (JASP Team, 2025). Descriptive statistics summarized the respondents' demographic characteristics, educational profiles, and *academic performance* data. Weighted mean and standard deviation were determined to assess students' perceptions of the National Learning Camp's influence on their achievement in Mathematics. Additional qualitative data gathered were analyzed to support the numerical data analysis.

Scope and Delimitation of the Study

This study investigated the *perceived effectiveness* of the *National Learning Camp (NLC)* on the *academic performance* of students in mathematics. The research specifically examined the changes in *mathematics achievement* among Busok NHS students who participated in the NLC program during the school year 2024-25.

The study was limited to selected schools implementing the NLC program, focusing on middle and high school students. These schools included Busok National High, Bagumbayan NHS, Kapaya NHS, Bai Saripinang NHS, and Datu Matilondo Galmac NHS. It did not account for other academic subjects or learning camps outside the National Learning Camp framework. Additionally, the study did not cover long-term impacts on *academic performance* beyond the duration of the camp.

RESULTS

Table 2. Level of Effectiveness of NLC as Perceived by the Students in terms of *Engagement and Participation*

INDICATOR	Mean	SD	Descriptive Rating
<i>Engagement and Participation</i>			
1. I found the activities in the NLC to be very engaging.	5.79	0.68	Very Effective
2. I participated frequently in discussions during the NLC.	5.37	0.70	Very Effective
3. I greatly enjoyed working in groups during the NLC.	6.00	0.78	Very Effective
4. I was highly motivated to attend each session of the NLC.	6.17	0.76	Extremely Effective
5. I rated my overall participation in the NLC activities as high.	6.05	0.72	Very Effective
6. I often felt encouraged to ask questions during the NLC.	6.02	0.81	Very Effective
7. I found the use of technology in the NLC to be very engaging.	6.20	0.69	Extremely Effective
8. I rated the relevance of NLC activities to my interests as high.	5.53	0.73	Very Effective
9. I felt like my opinions were highly valued during the NLC.	5.81	0.85	Very Effective
10. I am very likely to recommend the NLC to my peers based on my engagement experience.	5.57	0.80	Very Effective
Section Mean	5.85	0.26	Very Effective

Table 3 Level of Effectiveness of NLC as Perceived by the Students in terms of Teacher Support

INDICATOR	Mean	SD	Descriptive Rating
<i>Teacher Support</i>			
1. My teachers were very supportive during the NLC.	6.46	0.66	Extremely Effective
2. Teachers provided feedback on my work frequently during the NLC.	6.32	0.72	Extremely Effective
3. I rated the clarity of instructions provided by teachers in the NLC as high.	6.38	0.68	Extremely Effective
4. I found my teachers to be very approachable during the NLC.	6.45	0.66	Extremely Effective
5. Teachers encouraged me to ask questions frequently during the NLC.	6.37	0.66	Extremely Effective
6. I rated the availability of teachers for additional help during the NLC as high.	6.44	0.61	Extremely Effective
7. Teachers were very supportive in helping me overcome challenges during the NLC.	6.41	0.65	Extremely Effective
8. I rated the effectiveness of teachers in managing classroom activities during the NLC as high.	6.75	0.68	Extremely Effective
9. Teachers promoted collaboration among students extensively during the NLC.	6.34	0.66	Extremely Effective
10. I am very likely to seek advice from teachers outside of the NLC based on my experience.	6.43	0.65	Extremely Effective
Section Mean	6.43	0.55	Extremely Effective

Table 4 Level of Effectiveness of NLC as Perceived by the Students in terms of Student Satisfaction

INDICATOR	Mean	SD	Descriptive Rating
<i>Student Satisfaction</i>			
1. I was very satisfied with the overall experience of the NLC.	6.50	0.50	Extremely Effective
2. I rated the relevance of the NLC content to my learning needs as high.	6.06	0.79	Very Effective
3. I greatly enjoyed the social interactions during the NLC.	6.47	0.50	Extremely Effective
4. I rated the quality of resources provided during the NLC as excellent.	5.92	0.83	Very Effective
5. I was very satisfied with the pace of learning during the NLC.	6.43	0.58	Extremely Effective
6. I rated the effectiveness of the NLC in addressing my learning gaps as high.	5.89	0.82	Very Effective
7. I felt appropriately challenged but not overwhelmed during the NLC.	5.94	0.83	Very Effective
8. I rated the variety of activities offered during the NLC as excellent.	5.94	0.79	Very Effective
9. I was very satisfied with the feedback from teachers during the NLC.	6.01	0.80	Very Effective
10. I am very likely to recommend the NLC to my peers based on my overall satisfaction.	5.94	0.82	Very Effective
Section Mean	6.11	0.24	Very Effective

Table 5. Level of Effectiveness of NLC as Perceived by the Students in terms of Resource Utilization

INDICATOR	Mean	SD	Descriptive Rating
<i>Resource Utilization</i>			
1. Resources were used very effectively during the NLC.	5.99	0.83	Very Effective
2. I rated the availability of necessary materials during the NLC as excellent.	6.02	0.80	Very Effective
3. The NLC made extensive use of technology to enhance learning.	5.56	1.14	Very Effective
4. I rated the maintenance and upkeep of facilities during the NLC as high.	5.39	1.11	Very Effective
5. The NLC utilized time for learning activities very effectively.	5.96	0.81	Very Effective
6. I rated the accessibility of digital tools during the NLC as excellent.	5.50	1.06	Very Effective
7. The NLC strongly encouraged the use of local resources for learning.	6.51	0.50	Extremely Effective
8. I rated the organization of resources to support different learning styles as excellent.	6.50	0.50	Extremely Effective
9. The NLC managed budget constraints very effectively to deliver quality education.	6.48	0.50	Extremely Effective
10. I am very likely to suggest improvements in <i>resource utilization</i> for future NLC sessions.	6.47	0.50	Extremely Effective
Section Mean	6.04	0.27	Very Effective

Table 6. Level of Effectiveness of NLC as Perceived by the Students in terms of *Continuity and Sustainability*

INDICATOR	Mean	SD	Descriptive Rating
<i>Continuity and Sustainability</i>			
1. I believe the NLC will continue to be effective in the future.	6.51	0.50	Extremely Effective
2. I rate the potential for the NLC to be replicated in other settings as high.	5.95	0.85	Very Effective
3. I believe the NLC will significantly contribute to long-term educational improvements.	5.47	1.13	Very Effective
4. I rate the level of community support for the NLC as strong.	6.49	0.50	Extremely Effective
5. The NLC effectively built partnerships with local organizations.	5.59	1.12	Very Effective
6. The NLC provided numerous opportunities for continuous learning beyond the program.	6.00	0.84	Very Effective
7. I rate the level of parental involvement in supporting the NLC's goals as high.	5.93	0.83	Very Effective
8. The NLC integrated effectively with existing educational systems.	5.08	0.80	Effective
9. I rate the potential for the NLC to adapt to changing educational needs as excellent.	6.52	0.50	Extremely Effective
10. I am very likely to support the continuation of the NLC in future years.	6.51	0.50	Extremely Effective
Section Mean	6.01	0.25	Very Effective

Table 7. Summary of the Level of Effectiveness of NLC as Perceived by the Students

INDICATOR	Mean	SD	Descriptive Rating
1 <i>Engagement and Participation</i>	5.85	0.26	Very Effective
2 <i>Teacher Support</i>	6.43	0.55	Extremely Effective
3 <i>Student Satisfaction</i>	6.11	0.24	Very Effective
4 <i>Resource Utilization</i>	6.04	0.27	Very Effective
5 <i>Continuity and Sustainability</i>	6.01	0.25	Very Effective
Grand Mean	6.09	0.14	Very Effective

Table 8. Emerging Themes of the Students' Perceived Effectiveness of the NLC

Emerging Themes	Quote from the Responses of the Participants
With Clustered Themes	
1. Activity-based engagement	- "Very Satisfied especially with activities like team quiz, and spin the wheel recitation." -p-1
- Engaging in group-based quizzes	- "It's fine. Group activities and toss coin recitation were fun." -p-7
- Participating in interactive recitations	
2. Social learning	- "Excited. Lots of group activities." -p-2
- Collaborating in group tasks	- "Happy and exciting. Teamwork is fun." -p-10
3. Instructional clarity and responsiveness	- "Maam explains the problems well. She doesn't get mad if you ask." -p-1
- Clarifying difficult topics	- "If you recite and you get the wrong answer, he doesn't get angry. Instead Maam explain it again." -p-6
- Responding patiently to questions	

4. Physical comfort and access	- "Ice breaker and electric fans are important in afternoon class." -p-5
- Improving classroom environment	- "The classroom is nice and has a water dispenser and fans so it's not too hot." -p-7
- Providing amenities	
5. Learning material engagement	- "Worksheets because there are examples and activities." -p-1
-Utilizing printed worksheets	- "The worksheets are ok but I wish they were smaller." -p-8
6. Digital content comprehension	- "...videos that maam prepares for class." -p-5
- Engaging with video resources	- "I hope the videos are in tagalog so it's easier to understand." -p-6
- Localizing instructional videos	
7. Learner self-efficacy	- "Yes. I'm reciting more in class." -p-1
- Boosting classroom participation	- "Yes. I'm not afraid to ask ma'am if I don't understand the class." -p-2
- Enhancing <i>academic performance</i>	- "Yes. Sometimes I can recite in class unlike before." -p-8
8. Long-term skill transfer	- "Yes. What we learned at NLC is very useful in the store and in class especially that memorization of multiplication table." -p-6
- Applying math rules in real contexts	
- Memorizing mathematical facts	- "Yes. It's is very useful at school and at work and in Mama's ukay-ukay business." -p-9 - "Yes, it's very useful. It's beneficial in our class and in our life especially in my fathers job as a carpenter." -p-10

Table 9. Academic Performance of the Students in Mathematics

School	Mean Grade	SD	Descriptive Rating
Busok NHS	82.15	1.91	Satisfactory
Bai Saripinang NHS	81.89	2.13	Satisfactory
Kapaya NHS	82.13	2.32	Satisfactory
Bagumbayan NHS	82.30	2.06	Satisfactory
Sumilil NHS	81.00	1.71	Satisfactory
Masiag NHS	82.14	2.14	Satisfactory
Datu Matilendo Galmac NHS	81.89	1.57	Satisfactory
Mean	82.05	0.13	Satisfactory

Table 10. Significant Relationship Between the Perceived Effectiveness of the National Learning Camp and Students' Academic Achievement in Mathematics

Variables	Mean	SD	r	P-value	Interpretation
<i>Perceived Effectiveness</i> of NLC	6.09	0.14	0.137	0.036	Significant Slight or Weak Correlation
<i>Academic Achievement</i>	82.05	2.02			

Table 11. Emerging Themes of the Students' Perception of the Influence of the National Learning Camp on Their Performance in Mathematics

Emerging Themes with Clustered Themes		Raw Statements
1. Topic recall		- "Interest and discounts is what I remember most." -p-1
-Remembering topics	specific	- "Lots of activities. Problem solving is terrible." -p-9

-Recalling activity types	- "Enjoy group activities. Multiply and divide manually and also with a percentage." -p-10
-Noting topic-related challenges	
2. Foundational skill acquisition	- "The sentence must be understood before the problem can be solved and the multiplication table must be memorized to solve it easily." -p-1
- Memorizing fundamental concepts	- "After NLC I memorized the multiplication table and I understood the percentage, fractions, interest and discounts a little better." -p-2
- Practicing fractional and percentage calculations	
3. Procedural mastery	- "When we were taught PEMDAS, I was happy because at last I know how to solve it." -p-7
- Applying order of operations rules	- "We were taught the rules of basic plus, minus, times, divide numbers with letters like $2x$, $11x$, $-2x$." -p-3
- Performing algebraic manipulations	
- Executing unit conversions	- "I already know how to convert. For example, km-m-cm, then percent to decimal." -p-4
- Mastering exponent and root operations	- "I know a little bit about the square and square root numbers." -p-6
4. Problem interpretation	- "The sentence must be understood before the problem can be solved..." -p-1
- Prioritizing sentence understanding	- "Teacher ways of explaining and instruction has help me understand solve mathematical problems." -p-10
- Employing step-by-step clarification	
5. Instructional support	- "You are given time to understand and Maam doesn't get angry when asked." -p-1
- Allowing student questions	- "If you don't know you can ask the teacher, then he lectures it again, and there are many examples." -p-4
- Providing work examples	
- Maintaining moderate pacing	- "The most helpful thing about NLC is that the teaching is not fast, and there are many examples." -p-10

- 6. Collaborative learning** - "In NLC, my classmates and I help each other." - p-7
- Helping classmates
 - Engaging in group tasks
- "Enjoy group activities." -p-10
- 7. Self-efficacy growth** - "I used to be afraid of math, but in NLC math is ok if you know it." -p-9
- Overcoming math anxiety
 - Recommending to peers- Gaining self-assurance
- "I will recommend this to my other classmates because it is good and you can learn a lot." -p-2
- "I'm pretty confident in math now and I can solve it quickly..." -p-5

Table 12. Challenges and Experiences of Students During the Conduct of the NLC

INDICATORS	Mean	SD	Descriptive Rating
1 I found the NLC very effective and helpful.	6.70	0.67	Extremely Effective
2 I was able to participate in the camp without encountering significant difficulties.	6.55	0.76	Extremely Effective
3 The materials provided during the NLC supported my learning.	6.79	0.56	Extremely Effective
4 I found the sessions easy to follow and understand.	6.68	0.68	Extremely Effective
5 I was able to apply what I learned.	6.69	0.67	Extremely Effective
6 I stayed motivated or focused during math sessions	6.57	0.70	Extremely Effective
7 I got help from my teachers and classmates when I did not understand something	6.81	0.54	Extremely Effective
8 I was still able to comprehend the lectures even though I had difficulties with mathematics during the Learning Camp.	6.42	0.83	Extremely Effective

9 Even though there were problems, I stayed positive and wanted to do math activities at the NLC.	6.43	0.81	Extremely Effective
10 The National Learning Camp gave me enough help in learning mathematics thoroughly.	6.53	0.76	Extremely Effective
Section Mean	6.62	0.13	Extremely Effective

Table 13. Emerging Themes of the Student Responses on the Challenges, Experiences, and Learning Outcomes in the *National Learning Camp (NLC)*

Emerging Theme	Raw Statements
Problem complexity	- "There are lot of problem solving in math. The problem is being reversed. English is sometimes confusing to understand." -p-1
- Facing complex problem formats	- "Lots of activities. Problem solving is terrible." -p-9
- Managing extensive problem sets	- "Some topics were hard for me to understand, especially when they were presented quickly or based on what I thought I already knew." -p-7
- Confronting multi-sentence problems	
Language comprehension	- "English is sometimes confusing to understand." -p-1-
- Navigating English mathematical statements	"Understanding english statement is really challenging." -p-10
- Lacking native language materials	- "Teacher instruction and videos were in tagalog or ilonggo for us to have a better understanding." -p-1
3. Cognitive fatigue	- "...plus I'm tired and sleepy in the afternoon." -p-2-
- Experiencing tiredness during sessions	"I'm sleepy and tired during math session because it's afternoon." -p-4
- Struggling with afternoon lethargy	- "I'm always sleepy. I don't understand and I'm tired to do math in the afternoon." -p-3

- 4. Math Anxiety**
- Feeling embarrassed or ashamed
 - Worrying about wrong answers
- “I used to worry about messing up, especially when I was in a group or when I had to solve a problem in front of other people.” -p-8
- “...fear of messing up especially during work presentation and group activities.” -p-10
- 5. Learning pace mismatch**
- Managing uneven pacing
- “It was sometimes challenging to keep up when others were faster, or to stay engaged when the pace was too slow.” -p-7
- 6. Instructional resource inadequacy**
- Desiring interactive digital tools
 - Seeking diversified media formats
 - Requesting practical, real-life examples
 - Calling for additional guidance and examples
- “Add math-related games, contests, or creative challenges to calm people down and get them excited.” -p-3
- “More interactive tools like math games, videos, and digital whiteboards too help us understand hard ideas better.” -p-4
- “Suggestion for more videos for lessons to be different. And it's nice to do group study and group work.” -p-2
- 7. Learning engagement disruption**
- Experiencing comprehension gaps
 - Inhibiting participation
- “If you don't understand, you won't be able to solve, you won't participate in group activities because you're ashamed, and you'll feel useless.” -p-1
- “When I was having trouble with certain ideas, I didn't feel as comfortable answering questions or doing group activities.” -p-8
- “I was afraid of giving the wrong answer, so I sometimes didn't speak up.” -p-10
- 8. Schedule misalignment**
- Conducting sessions during vacation time
 - Causing leisure conflicts
- “Least helpful is the vacation time yet you're still going to school.” -p-4
- “My suggestion is not to put the NLC on vacation time.” -p-5
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DISCUSSION

Table 2 presents the students' perceptions of the level of effectiveness of the *National Learning Camp (NLC)* in terms of *engagement and participation*. Based on the data, the overall section mean is 5.85 with a standard deviation of 0.26, which falls under the descriptive rating of "Very Effective." The result indicates that the students found the NLC a highly engaging and participatory experience.

Among the ten indicators, the highest-rated item was "I found the use of technology in the NLC to be very engaging," which garnered a mean score of 6.20 and a standard deviation of 0.69, interpreted as "Extremely Effective." It was followed by "I was highly motivated to attend each session of the NLC" ($M = 6.17$, $SD = 0.76$), which also received an "Extremely Effective" rating. These results suggest that both the integration of technology and the motivational aspects of the NLC were significant contributors to *student engagement*.

Other indicators also received high ratings. For example, students reported greatly enjoying group work ($M = 6.00$), feeling encouraged to ask questions ($M = 6.02$), and assessing their overall participation as high ($M = 6.05$). These were rated as "Very Effective," demonstrating the program's success in promoting active involvement and interaction. Notably, even the lowest-rated item, "I participated frequently in discussions during the NLC," had a mean of 5.37, which still falls within the "Very Effective" range. The result suggests that while there may be a slight improvement in facilitating verbal participation, *student engagement* remained generally strong.

Additionally, students felt that their opinions were highly valued ($M = 5.81$), and they expressed a willingness to recommend the program to others based on their engagement experience ($M = 5.57$). These findings further support that the NLC fostered a positive, inclusive, and meaningful learning environment.

These results underscore the effectiveness of the NLC in promoting *student engagement and participation*. The consistently high mean scores and relatively low standard deviations indicate a generally uniform and positive student perception. These findings highlight the value of the NLC as an educational strategy that effectively utilizes interactive activities, technology, and motivational approaches to enhance the learning experience.

Table 3 presents the students' assessment of the level of effectiveness of the *National Learning Camp (NLC)* regarding *teacher support*. The overall section mean was 6.43 with a standard deviation of 0.55, which falls under the "Extremely Effective." The result indicates that students perceived the support they received from teachers during the NLC as highly effective and meaningful in enhancing their learning experience.

Among the ten indicators, the highest mean score was observed in the item "I rated the effectiveness of teachers in managing classroom activities during the NLC as high," with a mean of 6.75. Although this item also had a relatively high standard deviation ($SD = 4.68$), it still received an "Extremely Effective" rating, emphasizing the positive

impression of the students regarding classroom management. Following this, students also gave high ratings to items such as "My teachers were very supportive during the NLC" (M = 6.46, SD = 0.66), "I found my teachers to be very approachable during the NLC" (M = 6.45, SD = 0.66), and "I rated the availability of teachers for additional help during the NLC as high" (M = 6.44, SD = 0.61). These results demonstrate the critical role that teacher presence, openness, and availability play in *student satisfaction*.

Students also highlighted consistent feedback and clarity of instruction from teachers, with mean scores of 6.32 and 6.38, respectively, suggesting that teachers effectively communicated expectations and offered ongoing guidance. Similarly, items related to teacher encouragement in asking questions (M = 6.37), support in overcoming challenges (M = 6.41), and fostering collaboration (M = 6.34) all received high marks, reinforcing the positive teacher-student interaction within the NLC.

The students expressed a strong willingness to seek advice from teachers even outside the NLC setting (M = 6.43, SD = 0.65), which may reflect a deep level of trust and rapport built during the program. This result also suggests the long-term benefits of the NLC experience in strengthening teacher-student relationships.

The consistently high ratings across all items support the conclusion that the NLC effectively provided robust *teacher support*. This element is a cornerstone of the program's success, contributing significantly to the students' academic engagement and personal development.

Table 4 presents the level of effectiveness of the *National Learning Camp (NLC)* as students perceive it in terms of *student satisfaction*. The section mean for *student satisfaction* was 6.11 with a standard deviation of 0.24, which is descriptively rated as "Very Effective."

Looking at the individual indicators, students reported the highest levels of satisfaction with their overall experience of the NLC (Mean = 6.50, SD = 0.50) and their enjoyment of social interactions during the NLC (Mean = 6.47, SD = 0.50), both rated as "Extremely Effective." Similarly, students were very satisfied with the pace of learning during the NLC (Mean = 6.43, SD = 0.58), also receiving an "Extremely Effective" rating.

Several other aspects of the NLC were perceived as "Very Effective" by the students. These include the relevance of the NLC content to their learning needs (Mean = 6.06, SD = 0.79), the quality of resources provided (Mean = 5.92, SD = 0.83), the effectiveness of the NLC in addressing their learning gaps (Mean = 5.89, SD = 0.82), feeling appropriately challenged but not overwhelmed (Mean = 5.94, SD = 0.83), the variety of activities offered (Mean = 5.94, SD = 0.79), the feedback received from teachers (Mean = 6.01, SD = 0.80), and their likelihood to recommend the NLC to their peers (Mean = 5.94, SD = 0.82). The relatively low standard deviations across all indicators suggest that the students' perceptions were generally consistent.

These findings indicate a high level of *student satisfaction* with the NLC, with students particularly satisfied with their overall experience, social interactions, and pace of learning.

Table 5 details the students' perceived level of effectiveness of the *National Learning Camp (NLC)* regarding *resource utilization*. The section mean for *resource utilization* was 6.04, with a standard deviation of 0.27, which is categorized as "Very Effective."

Examining the individual indicators, students expressed the highest levels of agreement with the NLC strongly encouraging the use of local resources for learning (Mean = 6.51, SD = 0.50), the excellent organization of resources to support different learning styles (Mean = 6.50, SD = 0.50), the very effective management of budget constraints to deliver quality education (Mean = 6.48, SD = 0.50), and their likelihood to suggest improvements in *resource utilization* for future NLC sessions (Mean = 6.47, SD = 0.50). All these indicators were rated as "Extremely Effective."

The remaining indicators were rated as "Very Effective," indicating a positive perception of *resource utilization*. These include the effective use of resources during the NLC (Mean = 5.99, SD = 0.83), the excellent availability of necessary materials (Mean = 6.02, SD = 0.80), the extensive use of technology to enhance learning (Mean = 5.56, SD = 1.14), the high rating of facility maintenance and upkeep (Mean = 5.39, SD = 1.11), the very effective utilization of time for learning activities (Mean = 5.96, SD = 0.81), and the excellent accessibility of digital tools (Mean = 5.50, SD = 1.06).

The findings suggest that students perceived *resource utilization* during the NLC as highly effective, particularly in encouraging local resources, organizing resources for diverse learning styles, managing budget constraints, and identifying potential future improvements.

Table 6 presents the students' perceptions regarding the *National Learning Camp (NLC)*'s level of effectiveness in terms of *continuity and sustainability*. The overall section mean for *continuity and sustainability* was 6.01, with a standard deviation of 0.25, corresponding to a "Very Effective" descriptive rating.

Looking at the individual indicators, students showed the strongest agreement with their belief that the NLC will continue to be effective in the future (Mean = 6.51, SD = 0.50), their rating of the potential for the NLC to adapt to changing educational needs as excellent (Mean = 6.52, SD = 0.50), their very high likelihood to support the continuation of the NLC in future years (Mean = 6.51, SD = 0.50), and their rating of the level of community support for the NLC as strong (Mean = 6.49, SD = 0.50). These four indicators were all rated as "Extremely Effective."

Several other indicators were rated as "Very Effective," suggesting a positive outlook on the NLC's *continuity and sustainability*. These include the perceived high potential for the NLC to be replicated in other settings (Mean = 5.95, SD = 0.85), the belief that the NLC will significantly contribute to long-term educational improvements (Mean =

5.47, SD = 1.13), the effectiveness of the NLC in building partnerships with local organizations (Mean = 5.59, SD = 1.12), the provision of numerous opportunities for continuous learning beyond the program (Mean = 6.00, SD = 0.84), and the rating of parental involvement in supporting the NLC's goals as high (Mean = 5.93, SD = 0.83). Though still positive, the indicator with the lowest rating was the perceived effective integration of the NLC with existing educational systems (Mean = 5.08, SD = 0.80), which was rated as "Effective." The slightly higher standard deviations for indicators related to long-term improvements and local partnerships suggest more varied student opinions on these aspects.

These findings indicate that students generally strongly believe in the *continuity and sustainability* of the NLC, particularly regarding its future effectiveness, adaptability, potential for continued support, and community involvement.

Table 7 summarizes the overall level of effectiveness of the *National Learning Camp (NLC)* as perceived by the students across five key indicators: *Engagement and Participation*, *Teacher Support*, *Student Satisfaction*, *Resource Utilization*, and *Continuity and Sustainability*. The grand mean across all indicators was 6.09 with a standard deviation of 0.14, which is descriptively rated as "Very Effective." The result indicates that students held positive perceptions of the NLC's effectiveness.

Specifically, *Teacher Support* received the highest mean rating of 6.43 (SD = 0.55), categorized as "Extremely Effective," suggesting that students highly valued the support they received from their teachers during the NLC. *Student Satisfaction* followed with a mean of 6.11 (SD = 0.24), *Resource Utilization* with a mean of 6.04 (SD = 0.27), and *Continuity and Sustainability* with a mean of 6.01 (SD = 0.25), all rated as "Very Effective." *Engagement and Participation* had the lowest mean among the five indicators at 5.85 (SD = 0.26) but was still rated as "Very Effective," indicating a generally positive level of student involvement. The low standard deviations across all indicators suggest a consistent pattern of student responses, indicating a consensus in their perceptions of the NLC's effectiveness in these areas.

A similar study by Nunez et al. (2022), as cited by Espinosa (2024), on the perceived effects of a National Learning Camp on Grade 7 and 8 learners in the Philippines also found positive perceptions among students regarding the learning camp's impact on various aspects, including interest in learning and socio-emotional skills. While that study focused on different specific domains, the overarching finding of positive student perception aligns with the "Very Effective" rating observed in this summary table. The result suggests that learning camp initiatives can foster positive student experiences and outcomes.

In Table 8 students described their experiences as fun and interesting, thanks to the collaborative quizzes and interactive recitations. Activities like "spin the wheel" and "toss a coin" recitations kept them engaged. The group assignments encouraged kids to participate and enjoy learning. Many students stated that peer group interaction made learning more enjoyable and less stressful. They valued participation in school activities because it provided a stronger sense of connection and comfort. Students observed their

teachers' patient explanations of difficult ideas and irritated replies to questions. This encouraging behavior created a sense of safety in children, urging them to investigate and take chances, even in the face of uncertainty.

The classroom atmosphere was important to the students. They reported that fans, water dispensers, and ice breaks made afternoon sessions more bearable and improved sustained concentration. Students found printed worksheets valuable since they included instant examples and exercises. These resources improved class comprehension and enabled self-paced review. Students welcomed using videos in lessons, although they wished for a greater quantity to be available in their native language, Tagalog. Videos in English were more difficult to understand, whereas resources in the local language accelerated learning.

After finishing the camp, students reported feeling more confident. They began attending class more frequently, showed less concern about mistakes, and demonstrated improvements in their skills, notably in mathematics. Students believed that the information they obtained was useful not only in academic settings but also in everyday life. They discussed the use of mathematics skills at home, in small businesses, and even their potential for future employment.

Activity-based engagement is paramount to students, as it converts passive learning into active participation, thereby substantially improving personal development, retention, and comprehension. It enhances understanding and retention, fosters critical thinking and problem-solving, increases motivation and interest, fosters collaboration and communication, fosters confidence and independence, and supports inclusive learning. Consequently, activity-based methods can be customized to accommodate a variety of learning styles and tempos. Inclusivity is essential for guaranteeing that all students have the chance to flourish.

Table 9 presents the *academic achievement* of students in Mathematics across seven National High Schools (NHS): Busok, Bai Saripinang, Kapaya, Bagumbayan, Sumilil, Masiag, and Datu Matilondo Galmac. All seven secondary schools exhibit relatively similar performance in Mathematics. Bagumbayan NHS recorded the highest mean grade of 82.30, closely followed by Busok NHS (82.15), Masiag NHS (82.14) and Kapaya NHS (82.13). Bai Saripinang NHS and Datu Matilondo Galmac NHS have a mean grade of 81.89. Sumilil NHS has the lowest mean grade among the listed schools, at 81.00.

Despite the slight variations in mean grades and standard deviations across the individual schools, all are rated "Satisfactory" in descriptive rating. The result suggests that the criteria for the descriptive rating likely have a threshold that encompasses the range of mean scores observed.

The overall mean grade is 82.05, with a very small standard deviation of 0.13. This small standard deviation for the overall mean indicates that the average performance in Mathematics is quite consistent across all the schools considered in this table. The overall

descriptive rating is also "Satisfactory," consistent with the ratings of the individual schools.

The *academic achievement* of students in Mathematics across the seven National High Schools is generally satisfactory, with mean grades hovering around the low 80s. The overall average performance is uniform, leading to a consistent "Satisfactory" descriptive rating for all schools.

Several studies mention "satisfactory" or "fairly satisfactory" levels of mathematics performance among high school students. A study by Lumantas (2017) in Cebu City, Philippines, also found that most students' mathematical performance fell within the "Satisfactory and Fairly Satisfactory" categories.

The result presented in Table 10 reveals a statistically significant but *weak positive correlation* between students' perception of the effectiveness of the *National Learning Camp (NLC)* and their *academic achievement* in Mathematics, with a correlation coefficient of $r = 0.137$ and a p-value of 0.036. Since the p-value is less than 0.05, the result is considered statistically significant, implying that students' perceptions are meaningfully associated with their academic outcomes, although to a limited extent.

The data show that students perceived the NLC's effectiveness as relatively high, with a mean score of 6.09 (SD = 0.14). This suggests that most students viewed the program positively, citing its engaging activities, supportive teachers, and helpful learning environment. Likewise, students attained an average academic score of 82.05 (SD = 2.02) in Mathematics, indicating satisfactory performance.

The positive direction of the correlation indicates that as students' perception of the NLC's effectiveness improves, their *academic achievement* in Mathematics also tends to increase slightly. The result implies that a favourable view of the program may be linked to better motivation, increased participation, and more meaningful engagement with mathematical concepts, factors that enhance learning outcomes.

However, the weak correlation strength also signals that while perception has a measurable impact, it is not the sole factor influencing *academic performance*. Other external and internal factors, such as socio-economic status, prior knowledge, attendance, home responsibilities, and teaching quality, may also significantly shape student achievement. Therefore, while enhancing students' experience and satisfaction with the NLC is important, it should be complemented by broader interventions aimed at addressing the holistic needs of learners.

This result supports the relevance of continuously improving the implementation of the NLC by integrating strategies that promote engagement and academic rigor, inclusivity, and contextual responsiveness to learners' circumstances.

Wu and Wu (2019) conducted a study involving 215 students in Taiwan to evaluate the effectiveness of a game-based learning environment called Math-Island. The study

found that students participating in the Math-Island program significantly improved *mathematics achievement*, particularly in calculation and word problem-solving skills.

In table 11, the qualitative responses gathered from the student participants provided valuable insights into how the *National Learning Camp (NLC)* influenced their learning and performance in Mathematics. Several key themes emerged from the interview data, reflecting different dimensions of their experiences, understanding, and perceptions of the NLC.

Many students recalled specific mathematical concepts and activities that stood out to them, including lessons on multiplication tables, area, and perimeter, converting units of measurement, and solving percentage problems. These topics were often presented through engaging and practical examples, such as applying discounts in grocery purchases or measuring classroom items, which made the lessons more relatable and easier to understand. Such real-life contexts appeared to deepen student comprehension and interest in mathematical concepts.

Most students responded positively when asked about how the NLC affected their understanding and ability in Mathematics. They reported improved problem-solving ability, application of formulas, and recall of fundamental concepts.

Several participants emphasized their improved confidence, noting that they felt more equipped to engage in mathematical tasks during and after the NLC. In particular, skills such as translating word problems into equations and converting mathematical units were initially identified as challenging. Still, they became more manageable through repetitive practice and teacher guidance during the camp. One participant highlighted that the NLC helped reduce their fear of the subject, which had been a barrier to learning in the regular classroom.

Furthermore, students found the instructional methods used during the NLC notably effective. The approachable demeanour of teachers, extended instructional time, and small group activities fostered a positive learning environment. Students valued the opportunity to ask questions without judgment and appreciated the detailed explanations provided by instructors. Despite some challenges, such as the inconvenience of attending school during vacation and repeating known topics, the overall sentiment was that the NLC was a meaningful and beneficial intervention.

Most notably, participants expressed that the NLC helped build their confidence in Mathematics, contributing to a greater willingness to engage in classroom discussions and solve problems independently. The structured review of foundational skills and enrichment activities appeared to fill learning gaps and support academic recovery. As a result, several students recommended the NLC to peers, particularly those struggling in Mathematics, emphasizing its role in reinforcing key concepts and improving academic outcomes.

The data indicate that the NLC provided students with clear, structured, and engaging instruction in Mathematics, allowing them to revisit and strengthen foundational concepts. As a direct result of their participation, students perceived increased confidence and competence in solving mathematical problems. Supportive teaching methods and contextualized lessons were highly appreciated, contributing to students' positive attitudes and improved achievement in Mathematics. Despite *logistical challenges*, the overall perception of the NLC was positive, with many students recognizing its importance in their academic development.

These findings suggest that intervention programs like the National Learning Camp can effectively enhance student achievement in Mathematics. Incorporating real-life applications, interactive activities, and responsive teaching fosters a supportive learning environment, especially for learners with prior academic difficulties. Schools may consider adopting similar programs during intersessions or as part of remedial strategies to address learning gaps and improve outcomes. Furthermore, the study highlights the need for learner-centered, flexible instruction that builds skill and confidence, critical components in addressing mathematics anxiety and underachievement.

A study by Insorio and Manalo (2025) evaluated the *National Learning Camp (NLC)* from the perspectives of mathematics teachers and students. The findings revealed that both groups perceived the NLC as effective in enhancing learning activities, materials, support, and outcomes. However, challenges were noted, including errors in printed materials, broad topics, and time-consuming preparation of instructional materials. Students also reported difficulties with unclear printed materials and overwhelming content. Supplementary YouTube video lessons were developed based on student suggestions to address these issues.

In Table 12, the mean scores increase from 6.42 to 6.81, all indicators were "Extremely Effective". The highest-rated item was "I got help from my teachers and classmates when I did not understand something" (Mean = 6.81, SD = 0.54), while the lowest-rated was "I was still able to comprehend the lectures even though I had difficulties with mathematics during the Learning Camp" (Mean = 6.42, SD = 0.54). The section mean of 6.62 shows high *perceived effectiveness* across all indicators.

Table 13 presents the thematic organization of student responses regarding their experiences and challenges in the *National Learning Camp (NLC)*, particularly about learning outcomes in mathematics.

Participants commonly expressed *enjoyment and Engagement*, many of whom described the NLC as exciting, fun, and motivational. They noted that group activities and classroom dynamics contributed to a lively atmosphere, encouraging participation. Learning and Readiness also emerged as a theme, with students acknowledging that the NLC expanded their mathematical knowledge and prepared them better for future academic work.

However, several barriers also became apparent. Anxiety, English comprehension, and classroom discomfort were hindrances to full participation. In addition, *household responsibilities* and *low motivation* due to the vacation mindset interfered with consistent attendance and focus. Some students highlighted teacher-related issues, stating that a teacher's mood or attitude influenced their learning motivation. These difficulties directly affected learning outcomes, including limited understanding of lessons, reduced participation, and missed instruction due to absences or fatigue.

Despite these challenges, a few students demonstrated resilience and a growth mindset, expressing a willingness to review, practice, and persist. Their responses suggest that a positive and supportive environment helps buffer academic struggles. Furthermore, students provided constructive suggestions for improvement, advocating for more interactive and real-life-based teaching strategies, multimedia tools, shorter but focused sessions, smaller class sizes, and a more encouraging classroom environment.

In the qualitative study of Bacong et al. (2023). They explored the struggles and challenges high school students face in learning mathematics. Using Interpretative Phenomenological Analysis, they identified several key themes: Cognitive Challenges: Students reported difficulties recalling previous lessons and understanding mathematical concepts, leading to perceiving mathematics as a highly challenging subject. Affective Factors: A lack of self-efficacy and motivation was prevalent among students, contributing to a tendency to give up easily when faced with mathematical problems. Contextual Influences: Environmental factors, such as classroom dynamics and teaching methods, impact students' engagement and learning in mathematics.

In summary, while students found the NLC to be an enjoyable and enriching learning environment, many faced socioeconomic and *logistical challenges* that negatively affected their ability to learn mathematics effectively. Group learning and *teacher support* were motivating factors, but inconsistent attendance and external responsibilities disrupted learning. Students desired more interactive, engaging, and supportive instructional methods tailored to their needs.

Thus, the *perceived effectiveness* of the *National Learning Camp (NLC)* in students' *academic performance* and their experiences in learning mathematics indicates that students predominantly view the NLC as advantageous to their education. It augments their interest in mathematics, curiosity, and motivation to learn, which are essential to *academic performance*. These affirmative dispositions enhance the learning experience, potentially improving *academic performance*.

The NLC additionally fosters socio-emotional growth and self-efficacy. Students indicated enhanced self-confidence, resilience, and a growth mindset, which are crucial for surmounting challenges in subjects such as mathematics. These characteristics enable students to endure difficulties and maintain confidence in their capacity for success.

Collaborative activities during the NLC facilitated peer learning, enabling students to interpret problems more effectively and develop procedural understanding. The result supports the notion that collaborative learning environments can improve *academic performance* and *student engagement*.

The perceived efficacy of the NLC is intricately linked to students' *academic achievement* and experiences in mathematics education. The program demonstrates the potential to enhance motivation, self-efficacy, and engagement; however, its efficacy relies on overcoming instructional challenges and ensuring clarity, sustainability, and appropriate pacing of learning materials and contextualized lessons.

These findings suggest that for programs like the NLC to maximize their impact, there should be a balance between academic enrichment and student well-being. Practical interventions such as differentiated instruction and improved teacher training can help ensure more equitable access and stronger learning outcomes in mathematics.

Additionally, listening to student voices can guide the development of more responsive and effective education programs.

Conclusions

Based on the findings of the study, several important conclusions can be drawn regarding the effectiveness and impact of the NLC program. Students generally perceived the NLC as highly effective, particularly valuing the strong support provided by teachers and the high level of *student engagement* fostered within the program. This positive perception, however, was not fully reflected in *academic achievement* in Mathematics, which was found to be satisfactory but not exceptional. The data suggest that while the NLC has a beneficial influence, there is still room for improvement in terms of student performance outcomes.

Furthermore, the study revealed that students encountered a range of logistical and socio-emotional challenges that limited their ability to participate fully and benefit from the program. These challenges likely contributed to the gap between perceived program effectiveness and actual *academic achievement*. Despite these obstacles, the NLC was found to have a positive impact on students' mathematical skills and their confidence in the subject, indicating that the program does play a valuable role in supporting student growth.

Interestingly, the analysis identified a statistically significant but weak correlation between students' perceptions of the program's effectiveness and their *academic achievement*. This suggests that while students' positive experiences are important, other factors—such as personal circumstances, external support, and individual learning differences—also play a significant role in determining academic success. Finally, student feedback provided practical suggestions for improving the NLC, highlighting areas such as program structure, resources, and support systems that could be enhanced to further boost outcomes in future implementations. Overall, the study underscores the value of

the NLC while pointing to the need for continued refinement and support to maximize its benefits for all students..

Recommendations

Based on the findings and conclusions, the researcher presents the following recommendations:

1. Sustain and enhance teacher-student interaction quality by providing continuous professional development focused on learner engagement strategies, feedback techniques, and motivational teaching practices.
2. Introduce advanced and remedial modules tailored to different proficiency levels, allowing high-performing students to be challenged further and struggling students to receive additional support to move beyond satisfactory levels.
3. Implement holistic support systems such as transportation assistance, feeding programs, mental health services, and family engagement initiatives to mitigate barriers that affect learning continuity and participation.
4. Expand the use of contextualized, real-life problem-solving activities and confidence-building strategies, such as peer mentoring and performance recognition, further to reinforce students' skills and self-efficacy in Mathematics.
5. Conduct follow-up evaluations to identify and address other influential factors, such as home environment, instructional time, and student readiness, and use data-driven insights to refine the program for more impactful academic outcomes.
6. Strengthen support services, integrate differentiated learning, enhance teacher training, use interactive and real-life activities, leverage multimedia tools, and do further research to enhance students' achievement in Mathematics.

Compliance with Ethical Standards

The researchers affirm that every ethical standard was meticulously observed during the conduct of the study. Prior to their participation, all participants gave their informed consent and were guaranteed the freedom to leave the study at any moment without facing any repercussions. All respondents' confidentiality and anonymity were preserved during the course of the study. There were precautions taken to protect the participants' health and make sure that their involvement did not cause them any harm. In conducting this study, the researchers affirm that they have no conflicts of interest. All sources were correctly mentioned, and plagiarism was absolutely prohibited. Additionally, there was no prejudice and the results were interpreted objectively. The results of this study were used solely for academic and research purposes.

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